

How to become expert but fluid

Lee seonwoo

I will tell you how to be good at something and how to apply it well. I will explain it with an example with a math problem. It is a method that can be used in other fields as well. First of all, you need to know the types of math problems. And you need to know each solution of those types. At this time, when you study solving methods, you have to figure out why and how you came up with the solution, the thinking process . Try to guess several of the thinking processes, experiment with other problems, and have them if you succeed. When you gather ideas like that, you have to combine and match them with each other to extract and figure out common ideas. And you have to figure out what situations the common thinking can be used in comprehensively. When you extract common thoughts like this, you can solve various problems

without having to memorize what to do in certain situations and what to do in certain situations, and your application will improve even if it is less accurate than memorizing them all. Because it is more comprehensive and I extracted them around thoughts.